

Aug 22, 2016

SNA medium

 In 1 collection

DOI

<https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.fmhbk36>

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OPEN ACCESS

DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.fmhbk36>

Protocol Citation: Remco Stam 2016. SNA medium. **protocols.io** <https://dx.doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.fmhbk36>

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Protocol status: Working

Created: August 19, 2016

Last Modified: March 28, 2018

Protocol Integer ID: 3465

Keywords: alternaria solani cultivation, sna medium growth medium, alternaria solani, sna medium, cultivation, growth, medium

Abstract

Growth Medium used for *Alternaria Solani* cultivation

First described: Nirenberg 1981

Materials

MATERIALS

 Distilled Water

 Agar

 1 M NaOH

 Glucose

 Potassium Chloride

 Monopotassium phosphate

 Potassium nitrate

 Magnesium sulfate heptahydrate

 Sucrose

Troubleshooting

1 Dissolve all salts and other ingredients in 1l of distilled water:

KN₂PO₄ 1g

KNO₃ 1g

MgSO₄-7H₂O 0.5g

KCl 0.5g

Glucose 0.2g

Sucrose 0.5g

2 Add 22 g of Kobe Agar

3 Bring pH to about 5.5 using approx. 600 µl NaOH

4 Autoclave at 15 psi for 20 min